

The Self-paced Learning Using Google Classroom

By:
Siti Nurul Baitina
Sutiah

What is Google Classroom ?

Google Classroom is a Learning Management System (LMS) issued by Google, so it is integrated with other Google products such as Gmail, Drive, Hangout, Meet, YouTube, and Calendar. This LMS can be used to deliver teaching materials and provide tests that are integrated with assessment. Students can also access it via any browser on desktop and mobile devices (Android and Apple). Suitable for lecturers who need to open online classes in asynchronous mode (non real-time).

POV:Tutor

→ Home Page

Question tag

If we want to ask for information we usually use the standard question form. However, sometimes we just want to keep a conversation going, or confirm information. In this case, question tags are often used to solicit input or confirmation to what we are saying. Using question tags well also promotes a keen understanding of the use of various auxiliary verbs.

Question tags, also tail questions, transform regular declarative clauses into questions. We use them to invite a response or confirmation from the person we are speaking to. Question tags are formed by adding an auxiliary verb and repeating the subject of the main clause as a pronoun. It's important to know which auxiliary verb to use and whether the tag should be positive or negative.

The aim of the course: Developing active and passive knowledge of the use of question tag.

Outcomes :

- At the end of this Module, Pupils should be able to know:
- Meaning of question tags
- How and when to use question tags

 Question Tags.docx

 Answering Question Tags.docx

 Question Tag at the End of the Imperative.docx

 Same-Way Question Tags.docx

 Question Tag (Quiz)

Introduction

Core

Materi

← Question Tags.docx

Question Tags

1. What is question tag?
The question tag is a short question that is added to the end of a statement (declarative sentence) to ask for confirmation of what has just been said. For example: I like cinema, don't I?
In general, question tags are a part that is often used in spoken English daily conversations.
2. Question tag formula
Question tag (+) linking verb "to" / auxiliary verb "to" + "question".

declarative sentence	question tag
I	is
you	are
she	is
he	is
we	are
they	are

Based on the general rule (general table), the positive question tag, use before the negative sentence (negative sentence). For vice versa, negative question tag, use before positive sentence (positive sentence).

A. Example of a Question Tag Exercise:

negative sentence, positive question tag	positive sentence, negative question tag
You don't have much, do you? (Kamu tidak punya banyak, ya?)	You have much, don't you? (Kamu punya banyak, bukan?)
Almost didn't come late, did he? (Hampir tidak datang terlambat, kan?)	Almost came late, didn't he? (Hampir datang terlambat, kan?)
The class isn't busy, is it? (Pria itu tidak sibuk, kan?)	The class is busy, isn't it? (Pria itu sibuk, bukan?)
You haven't finished your homework, have you?	You have finished your homework, haven't you?

isn't (Kamu tidak sibuk, kan?)	isn't (Kamu tidak sibuk, kan?)
They aren't attend the seminar, will they? (Mereka tidak akan menghadiri seminar, kan?)	They will attend the seminar, won't they? (Mereka akan menghadiri seminar, kan?)

Quiz

docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FA...

Question Tag (Quiz)

Answer the quiz for completed your course
* Wajib

Alamat email *

Email Anda

Name *

Jawaban Anda

He will be coming? * 10 poin

Is he

Doesn't he

Did he

Won't he

docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FA...

Question Tag (Quiz)

Thank you for your submission.

If you passed you will receive a printable certificate shortly.

Lihat skor

[Kirim tanggapan lain](#)

Kerjakan lebih banyak atau dukung kami dengan Google, Lazada, Tokopedia, Shopee, dan lainnya.

Google Formulir

POV: Student

A screenshot of a mobile application interface showing a document titled 'Question tag'. At the top, there is a back arrow and a vertical ellipsis. The title 'Question tag' is displayed below a horizontal line. The main content area contains two paragraphs of text. The first paragraph explains that question tags are used to solicit input or confirmation. The second paragraph explains that question tags transform regular declarative clauses into questions. Below the text, there is a section titled 'The aim of the course: Developing active and passive knowledge of the use of question tag.' followed by 'Outcomes :'. The outcomes are listed as: '-At the end of this Module, Pupils should be able to know:', '-Meaning of question tags', and '-How and when to use question tags'. At the bottom, there is a list of documents with document icons: 'Question Tags.docx', 'Answering Question Tags.docx', 'Question Tag at the End of the Imperative.docx', 'Same-Way Question Tags.docx', and 'Question Tag (Quiz)'.

Thanks!

Link :
<https://classroom.google.com/c/MTg2MzQzNzI4NTU4?cjc=np52vxe>

Class code: np52vxe

Reference:

Edunex ITB. 2020. *Google Classroom Panduan Mengelola Kelas Daring*.